

MICR PLASTICS

Plastic in Agricultural Production:
Impacts, Lifecycles and **LONG**-term Sustainability

NEWSLETTER N°3 - October 2023

THEY ARE EVERYWHERE

**Microplastics are
conspicuous and
abundant
anthropogenic
contaminants of soils.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000210

<https://www.papillons-h2020.eu/>

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With summer holidays already far behind us and fall finally arriving, PAPILLONS H2020 project welcomes you to the third newsletter! Clustering and creating linkages with other projects, presenting scientific results at the European Commission, and boosting engagement are just few of the key message for our #3 Newsletter.

In this newsletter you will find some relevant updates and news about what is going on in the life of the PAPILLONS project, such as our workshop in Piacenza under the AGRIFOODPLAST conference and our new platform on Zenodo.

Feel free to read through it and contact us if you wish to contribute to the project as a stakeholder or want to learn more about micro & nanoplastics in agricultural soil.

- PAPILLONS TEAM

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PAPILLONS (entitled 'Plastic in Agricultural Production: Impacts, Life-cycle and LONG-term Sustainability') is a research project supported by the European Commission within the EU Horizon 2020 programme.

Our consortium is built of 21 partners from 16 countries, who represent the cutting edge of research into agricultural plastic use and impacts in Europe. We comprise a network of world leading experts, including excellence in agronomy, ecotoxicology, soil, animal and plant ecology, material sciences, social sciences, economics and environmental chemistry.

Plastics are becoming increasingly important in European agricultural production. However, the long-term impacts of agricultural plastic materials on soil ecosystem quality and functioning, and agricultural sustainability is uncharted and unknown. What PAPILLONS aims at is to understand the impacts of the use of plastic materials in EU agricultural soil, i.e., the release of micro & nano-plastics and chemicals and how soil health & productivity is affected.

This way it can contribute to knowledge development and deliver information for farmers, industries, regulators and policy makers to introduce practices, products and instruments that guarantee the safe & sustainable use of agricultural plastics in our soil systems.

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Intensive clustering activities over the last months

PAPILLONS' team believe in the importance of connecting with other international projects which share the same goals and values. Establishing long-term cooperation and sustainable dialogues with various clusters is an incredible opportunity to boost scientific research, amplify project results and spread PAPILLONS mission far & beyond. In the past months, PAPILLONS team had several meetings with 4 innovative projects.

On July 12th, our team met PLASTICHEAL is a H2020 project that aims at developing innovative tools to study the impact and mode of action of micro and nanoplastics on human health.

Mostly focused on nano-plastics, the project scope is to address the human's risk of exposure to MNPLs due to their ubiquitous presence in the environment.

On June 15th, Dr. Luca Nizzetto and Dr. Rachel Hulrey had a meeting with GCRF Agricultural Plastic, a UK based project.

The main goal of the consortium is to address the following question: "Do agricultural microplastics undermine food security and sustainable development in developing countries ?" This meeting was the first step towards an intensive collaboration which will mostly focused on clarifying and harmonising the soil terminology in the research community while covering the Knowledge gap PAPILLONS team aims to fulfill.

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Mobilising energies to overcome the challenges & find game changing solutions

Not one, but two meetings in less than two months with NoWaste - Agri-Plastic Circular Platform. During our first meeting at the end of march, NoWaste representatives provided an overview of their business-model. The scope of the platform is to contribute to help farmers and recyclers in addressing the valuing of agricultural waste by enhancing circularity. No Waste has developed an IT platform that connects actors in the agricultural plastic value chain, providing a model and tool box that can turn water into a resource.

At the current stage, their innovative solution, which can be a game changer in agricultural plastic waste management, is mostly focused on specific areas of Israel - their home-country. However, for PAPILLONS teams this meeting was not enough so... Inspired by NoWaste - Agri-Plastic Circular start-up, we met AGAIN! More representatives of our team joined the meeting to ask details on materials, means of transportations, etc.

Expanding their model to western countries, providing them the network and the linkages with interested stakeholders, etc. were the big discussion topics!

A little spoiler: some PAPILLONS partners met in Sicily to discuss future collaborations. [Click here](#) to discover more!

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Plastic pollution is a 360° challenge

On June 13th, PAPILLONS team turned towards the aquatic sphere; indeed, we discussed with LabPlas H2020 Project (titled 'Land-Based Solutions for Plastics in the Sea') representatives. We had the opportunity to explore common goals and overlapping scientific research with Cynthia Gomez, Project Manager of LabPLas and Professor Ricardo Beiras. Plastic pollution is a 360° challenge which break through any boundaries; the consequences affects both the terrestrial and marine ecosystems. Coordinating activities and research between projects that study plastic pollution in terrestrial and marine environment is useful to solve the questions score the environmental flows and budgets of this pollution and take coordinated action to effectively prevent it. Nothing can help more than joint collaboration and understanding of missions!

On August 21st, we had another clustering activity with SOILGUARD project. With PAPILLONS team, they share the goal to improve the overall soil health and foster more sustainable soil management practices. In particular, SOILGUARD team explained how they are taking advantage of modelling and simulations to understand how climate change can affect soil.

Thanks to the several field experiments across Europe, they will get several outcomes. Together we aim at supporting each other's policy recommendations and underlining the urgency of changes needed at the European level.

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Intensive meetings with the European Commission

On June 9th, 2023, PAPILLONS representatives had the opportunity to discuss and present some of the preliminary results obtained to the European Commission, specifically DG Agriculture and Rural and DG Environment.

These meetings took place with the participation as well of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

Thanks to a series of studies conducted on both the effects of micro and nano-plastics from non-biodegradable and biodegradable plastics on soil ecosystems, PAPILLONS team provided scientific proves the MNPs are the most conspicuous and abundant anthropogenic contaminants of soils.

These key messages from the meetings underlines the urge for a united call for strong actions to stop this contamination on agricultural soils across Europe.

During the meeting, PAPILLONS team conveyed their commitment to provide scientific results; indeed the research team is working to integrate critical research on plastic pollution into the upcoming EU Soil health law.

[Click here](#) to read PAPILLONS full statement after our EU Commission meetings!

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PAPILLONS support to the Food & Agriculture Organization action on agricultural plastics

PAPILLONS and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) have been closely working to inform the the upcoming Voluntary Code of Conduct on the sustainable use of plastics in agriculture, especially in relation to Council recommendation for FAO to undertake further scientific and evidence-based assessments related to the distribution, benefits, trade-offs and risks of plastics for agricultural use and their alternatives, and to address knowledge gaps on plastics in agriculture. Since we value stakeholders perspectives and experiences, we believed that a joint survey was the best option to raise the voice of these visions. The main aims of the survey were to “Map the views of stakeholders regarding their positioning on the current and future usage of plastics in agricultural production”.

Creating a gap matrix to illustrate gaps and overlaps between research on agricultural plastics and stakeholders’ concerns and needs. In collaboration with several FAO experts, we wrote a paper addressing knowledge gaps and offering multi-stakeholder perspectives on Agricultural Plastics. This paper is currently undergoing the peer review process for publication in an international journal.

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Creating a matrix

FAO mission towards the development of a Voluntary Code of Conduct on the sustainable use of plastics in agriculture stems from the fact that 'the use of plastics in agrifood value chains is pervasive and FAO estimates that every year 12.5 million tonnes of plastic products are used in plant and animal production. The crop production and livestock sectors are the largest users, accounting for 10 million tonnes per year, followed by fisheries and aquaculture with 2.1 million tonnes, and forestry with 0.2 million tonnes'. Effective and efficient solutions to stop plastic pollution in the agricultural sectors require simultaneous mobilisation of policies, technologies, sustainable practices, and stakeholders using principles of circular economy as a part of a transformation of agrifood systems.

In order to make sure that this manual will be accountable and useful, FAO called for a high level meeting 'Global Expert Meeting for the development of a Voluntary Code of Conduct on the sustainable use of plastics in agriculture'. PapiLLONS project was represented by Dr. Luca Nizzetto which was invited to join this high level forum to provide his wide range and meaningful perspective on the topic.

Moreover, the close collaboration with FAO representatives goes hand in hand with PAPILLONS activities; indeed, during our joint stakeholder workshop with MINAGRIS, Agricultural Plastics and Sustainability Specialist at FAO, Ms. Giulia Carcasci, participated as keynote speaker to the event providing incredible insights for the ongoing work and further inviting PAPILLONS team to share its findings to finalised the Voluntary Code of Conduct on the sustainable use of plastics in agriculture.

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INTERVIEW

In March, Aristeidis Tsagkaris, PhD, post-doc at the University of Chemistry and Technology in the Czech Republic, which is involved in several tasks under WP2 and WP3, answered to some very interesting questions.

On February 24th 2023, in collaboration with other researchers, they published a paper on 'The measurement of food safety and security risks associated with micro- and nanoplastic pollution'.

Since he has extensive expertise in the field of contaminants analysis, development and validation of both targeted and non-targeted methods, we asked him how MNPLs enters the human food chain and what kind of consequences this brings.

Moreover, he provided an in-depth overview of the major research gaps on which PAPILLONS research area is focusing and how these research gaps are hindering the development of robust risk assessments of MNP pollution.

Read the full interview in our [website!](#)

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PAPILLONS & Minagris Workshop and the Agrifoodplast conference

This PAPILLONS/MINAGRIS stakeholder workshop was held 15:30 - 18:30 (EET) on 12th September in Piacenza, Italy at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore in a hybrid form for both in-person and virtual attendees. The workshop was the concluding session of the first international Agrifoodplast Conference on micro- and nano-plastics in the agri-food chains which is taking place from the 10th-12th of September 2023.

This conference aimed at gathering international experts and keynote speakers to discuss various topics regarding the role of plastic in the agricultural sector. Indeed, among the topics, the sessions focused on: the impact of micro and nano-plastics on soil functions, exposure assessment in food, their toxicological and ecotoxicological effects in the overall agri-food chain. The topic was: A one-health approach for risk assessment of micro and nano-plastics. Through a One-Health lens, the workshop aimed to unpack the underlying potential toxic linkages caused by the agricultural plastic pollution which affect the agri-food chain, and ultimately human health. The workshop provided the platform for researchers, policymakers, industry representatives and other experts to discuss these topics, while providing an opportunity for our stakeholders to gain insights and participate in the debate. PAPILLONS and MINAGRIS projects presented their latest updates from their research activities and foreseen activities.

AGRIFOODPLAST

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A well connected consortium !

Since our second newsletter, we have been busy trying to understand how to better ameliorate your experience while navigating PAPILLONS online presence. You will read about the three big changes added to give you the best user experience!

PAPILLONS consortium has jointly decided to open the **PAPILLONS Community on ZENODO**. We aim at further ensuring the accessibility of our results, since our team stick to open-access resources and platforms in order. On this community you will find all publications funded under PAPILLONS project and all the public deliverables submitted and approved by the EU Commission. [Click here](#) to see all our publication in Zeondo Community!

A new 'Events' section? Yes!

A complete new outlook which reminds you of your calendar. This new format will help you easily identify all the events, and book your seats, while marking your personal agenda.

We do not spoiler you anything, so go [check yourself](#) our new layout and let us know that you think of the new features of the website

To help you navigate our **Knowledge Hub community**, we have introduced a new feature > TAGs <

Thanks to this new tool, you will be able to have a more accurate research in our website. Indeed, we know that soils, microplastics, etc. are very broad sectors; therefore, by clicking on your selected tag, you will be able to get the list of all contributions sorted by your criteria.

Our friends from Minagris and IKHAPP

The MINAGRIS project is another EU funded Horizon 2020 project on agricultural plastic use. They will also assess the impact of plastic debris in agricultural soils on biodiversity, plant productivity and ecosystem services and their transport and degradation in the environment.

They will provide tools and recommendations for sustainable use of plastic in agriculture at the farm and field levels for ensuring safe and economically viable food systems in Europe. Together with MINAGRIS, PAPILLONS will be holding joint stakeholder forum events!

International Knowledge Hub Against Plastic Pollution's (IKHAPP) mission is to collect, critically analyse and disseminate scientific knowledge to support effective policies and actions to fight plastic pollution globally. By providing a common platform, IKHAPP will give voice to this community.

The IKHAPP community assumes therefore a constructive role to inspire action and inform decisions through their work on Thematic Areas such as environment, society and technology.

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